

Saponins and Polyphenolics of Methanol Leaf Extract of *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch

Divine A. Onobrudu^{1*}

¹*Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Port Harcourt, P.M.B. 5323, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.*

Author's contribution

The sole author designed, analyzed and interpreted and prepared the manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: 10.9734/ACRI/2017/34716

Editor(s):

(1) Marco Aurelio Cristancho, Centre for Bioinformatics and Computational Biology, BIOS Parque los Yarumos Manizales, Caldas, Colombia.

Reviewers:

(1) Mostafa Abbas Shalaby, Cairo University, Egypt.

(2) Veerareddy, Hyderabad, India.

(3) Simone Carradori, University of Chieti-Pescara, Italy.

(4) Eliton da Silva Vasconcelos, Federal University of São Carlos, Brazil.

Complete Peer review History: <http://www.sciencedomain.org/review-history/20146>

Original Research Article

Received 7th June 2017
Accepted 6th July 2017
Published 21st July 2017

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to investigate saponins and polyphenolic constituents of methanol leaf extract of *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch. The qualitative phytochemistry was based on using reagents known to produce a particular color change which is distinct to that compound, while gas chromatography flame ionization detector (GC-FID) was used for the quantitative phytochemistry. The result revealed 24 polyphenolic compounds with protocatechuic acid (32.08%), catechin (23.77%), quercetin (8.35%), luteolin (20.15%) and kaempferol (12.79%) as the predominant constituents, and 11 phytocompounds of saponin with sapogenin (89.98%) and saponine (0.09%) being the predominant constituents. The experimental results indicate that the methanolic extract of *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch leaves could be a potent antioxidant agent.

Keywords: *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch; saponins; flavonoids; gas chromatography; antioxidant; phytochemistry.

*Corresponding author: Email: suoana2000@yahoo.com;

1. INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants represent a growing alternative to clinical medicine in the management of health challenges and diseases. Plant exhibits wide biological and pharmacological activities such as anti-inflammatory, diuretic, laxative, anti-spasmodic, anti-hypertensive and anti-microbial functions due to the presence of pharmacological bioactive phytoconstituents available in these plants. Flavonoids are natural polyphenolic compounds characterized by the presence of two benzene rings linked together with a heterocyclic pyran or pyrone ring [1] and play significant role in reducing the susceptibility to most disease [2]. Recent studies on saponins have shown anti-cancer activity, such as anti-proliferation, anti-metastasis, anti-angiogenesis, and reversal of multi-drug resistance (MDR) effects [3], suggesting that saponins are promising prospect for anti-cancer research and development. Hence, the need to investigate the saponins and polyphenolic phytoconstituents of methanol leaf extract of *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch.

The tree *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch known as the "frankincense tree" is a savannah forest plant which belongs to the family of *Burseraceae* [4]. The leaves are used medically as a diaphoretic, an expectorant prophylactic against fever [5]. Uzama *et al* [6] reported presence of moisture 12.24%, ash 7.43%, crude fibre 32.85%, crude lipids 20.41%, crude protein 1.00% and carbohydrate 26.07% in the leaf, and moisture of 8.51%, ash 14.23%, crude fibre 42.86%, crude lipid 14.23%, crude protein 0.40% and carbohydrate 19.56% in the tree bark [6]. The plant has been extensively studied for anti-microbial [7], antispasmodic [8], hepatoprotective [9], anti-cataract [10], mosquitocidal [11]. Therefore, *B. dalzielii* is a potential therapeutic plant, however only the quantitative phytochemistry of essential oils of *B. dalzielii* leaves have been investigated [4]. No study has been reported on the quantitative phytoconstituents of saponins and polyphenols of this plant hence this study was designed to determine the saponins and polyphenolic constituents present in *B. dalzielii* leaves.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The plant *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch was obtained from Maitunku hill, Bambam, Dadiya district of Gombe state. Plant was identified by Mr.Thlama Daniel Mshelbwala, Forestry Technology Department, Federal College of Forestry, Jos

and confirmed by Dr. Ekeke Chimezie, University of Port-Harcourt Reference Herbarium for Research and Germplasm Conservation, Department of Plant Sciences and Biotechnology, University of Port-Harcourt, Nigeria; where it was given the voucher number UPH/V/1247.

2.1 Methanol Extraction

The pulverized plant samples were extracted according to the method reported by Marita *et al*. [12]. The extract obtained was stored in an air tight plastic can.

2.2 Phytochemical Screening

2.2.1 Qualitative phytochemical analysis

Standard methods were used for the qualitative determination of saponins [13,14] and flavonoids [15]. This method involved using reagents known to produce a particular color change which is distinct to that particular compound.

2.2.2 Quantitative analysis of phytochemical constituents of flavonoids

2.2.2.1 Instrumentation

Hewlett Packard 6890 Flame Ionization detector Gas Chromatography system powered with ChemStation Rev.A09.01 [1206] software was used.

2.2.3 Quantitative analysis of phytochemical constituents of flavonoids

Extraction was carried out according to the method reported by Kone-Millogo *et al*. [16]. The gas chromatography conditions for flavonoid detection were; HP INNOWax column with (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μ m) dimension, split injection with split ratio of 20:1, nitrogen was the carrier gas with an inlet temperature of 250°C. The oven operated initially at 50°C. First ramping at 8°C/min for 20 min and maintained for 4 min, second Ramping at 12°C/min for 4 min and maintained for 4 min. A detector temperature of 320°C, hydrogen pressure of 22 Psi and compressed air of 35 Psi were used.

2.2.4 Quantitative analysis of phytochemical constituents of saponins

The extraction was carried out according to the modified method reported by Kone-Millogo *et al*. [16]. The extract was filtered and concentrated to 1.0 ml in the vial for gas chromatography analysis

and μl was injected into the injection part of the gas chromatography. The gas chromatography conditions for this analysis were; Capillary DB-225 MS column with dimension of (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μm), carrier gas was nitrogen, split injection with split ratio of 20:1 and an inlet temperature of 250°C were used. The oven program started with an initial temperature of 60°C for 5mins, first ramping at 12°C/min for 18 mins and the second ramping at 15°C/min for 5 mins. The detection temperature was 32°C, hydrogen pressure was 28 psi and compressed air was 40 psi.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis

This study showed that the leaves of *B. dalzielii* contain saponins and flavonoids.

3.2 Quantitative Gas Chromatographic Analysis of Saponins

The Gas chromatography analysis of the air dried leaves of *Boswellia dalzielii* gave a total saponin in a yield of 1.46 mg/100 g of the methanolic extract. Eleven compounds were identified with Sapogenin (89.98%) and saponine (0.09%) being the predominant compounds. The identified saponin compounds along with their retention time and composition are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Constituents of saponins in *B. dalzielii*

Constituents of saponin	Amount (mg/100 g) x 10 ⁴	Retention time (min)
Sapogenin	13176.9	22.59
Saponine	1451	26.28
Neochlorogenin	5.31	20.46
Diosgenin	2.51	19.51
Yanogenin	1.96	23.96
Tigogenin	1.66	20.11
Tribuloin	1.28	23.22
Conyzorgin	1.20	24.78
Hisopogenin	1.04	17.35
Hecogenin	0.94	21.43
Salogenin	0.86	18.76

3.3 Quantitative Gas Chromatographic Analysis of Flavonoids

Analysis of polyphenolic constituents of the methanolic extract yielded a total of 13.54

mg/100g. Twenty four compounds were identified with protocatechuic acid (32.08%), catechin (23.77%), quercetin (8.35%), luteolin (20.15%) and kaempferol (12.79%) being the predominant compounds. The identified saponin compounds along with their retention time and composition were presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Polyphenolic constituents of *B. dalzielii*

Constituents of flavonoids	Amount (mg/100g) x 10 ³	Retention time (min)
Protocatechuic acid	4346.11	11.37
Catechin	3220.37	13.81
Quercetin	1131.28	21.77
Luteolin	2730.27	17.31
Kaempferol	1732.68	18.53
Myricetin	351.48	25.16
Daidzein	9.98	15.89
Genistein	4.04	15.48
Butein	5.37	16.55
Epicatechin	4.10	19.50
Biochanin	2.03	17.07
Resveratrol	2.18	15.14
Gallocatechin	0.74	22.73
Robinetin	0.32	24.16
Epigallocatechin	0.61	20.63
Apigenin	0.14	16.01
Epicatechin-3-gallate	0.01	22.89
Isorhamnetin	0.08	23.35
(-)-Epigallocatechin-3-gallate	0.02	23.51
Eupalestin	0.05	25.39
Sinensetin	0.07	25.49
Biacalin	0.05	26.11

4. DISCUSSION

Identifying bioactive dietary constituents is an active area of scientific research that leads to new drug discovery. The main polyphenolic constituents of *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch are protocatechuic acid, catechin, quercetin, luteolin and kaempferol. Protocatechuic acid (3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid) is a phenolic acid which possess alleviating effect on inflammation, oxidation, hyperglycaemia, bacterial, cancer, ageing, tumour, asthma, ulcer and neuron [17-19]. Protocatechuic acid exhibited chemopreventive effect by inhibition of free radical generation, chelating metal transition

ions, scavenging free radicals via donation of hydrogen atom (H•) or electron (e) [20,21]. Reports have shown that catechins possess good alleviating properties for oxidation [22] and scavenging properties on varieties of free radicals such as reactive oxygen species *in-vitro* [23,24]. Kaempferol possess a double bond at C2-C3 in conjugation with an oxo group at C4, and the presence of hydroxyl groups at C3, C5 and C4, which are important structural features which makes it a potent anti-oxidant [2]. Furthermore, kaempferol is an inhibitor of the human monoamine oxidases (hMAO-A and hMAO-B) [25] and a potent superoxide scavenger, with an IC₅₀ of 0.5 μM [26]. Quercetin has the ability to scavenge free radicals, bind to transition metal ions due to the presence of pharmacophores and a catechol group found in ring B hence regarded as the most potent scavenger of 2 O⁻, and ONOO⁻ among the flavonoids [27] and improves glutathione concentrations [28,29]. The flavonol group of flavonoids can react with a free radical, it donates a proton and becomes a radical itself, but the resulting unpaired electron is delocalized by resonance, making the flavonol radical too low in energy to be reactive [30]. Sapogenin fraction of *Euphorbia nerifolia* leaf showed antioxidant and radio-protective activities [31].

5. CONCLUSION

The overall experimental results indicate that the methanolic extract of *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch leaves could be a potent antioxidant agent.

6. RECOMMENDATION

In view of the importance of herbal medicine to man, it is suggested that further study be carried out to elucidate the effect of these phytochemical constituents within the body and the degree and rate of absorption. The pathway of their metabolic conversions need to be identified and evaluated to accurately determine their effect *in vivo* and their effectiveness in preventing diseases arising from oxidative damage.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Author has declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

- Mari H, Riina N, Pia V, Marina H, Eeva M. Anti-inflammatory effects of Flavonoids. Mediators of Inflammation. 2007;1-10. Article ID 45673.
- Calderón-Montaño JM, Burgos-Morón E, Pérez-Guerrero C, López-Lázaro M. A review on the dietary flavonoid kaempferol. Mini-Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry. 2011;11:298-344.
- Xu XH, Li T, Fong CMV, Chen X, Chen XJ, Wang YT, Huang MQ, Lu JJ Saponins from Chinese medicines as anticancer agents. Molecules. 2016;21(1326):1-27.
- Kohoude MJ, Gbaguidi F, Agbani P, Ayedoun MA, Cozauxs S, Bouajila J. Chemical composition and biological activities of extract and essential oil of *Boswellia dalzielii* leaves. Journal of Pharmaceutical Biology. 2016;55(1): 33-42.
- Abdulazeez AT, Kabele-Toge B, Lawal M, Abubakar MG. Phytochemical, antibacterial and Toxicological studies of aqueous stem bark extract of *Boswellia dalzielii*. African Journal of Pharmaceutical Research Development. 2013;5(1): 61-67.
- Uzama D, Gbubele JD, Bwai MD, Kabir MG. Phytochemistry, nutritional and antimicrobial screening of hexane, ethyl acetate and ethanolic extract of *Boswellia dalzielii* leaves and bark. American Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering. 2015;3(5):76-79.
- Nwinyi FC, Binda L, Ajoku GA, Aniagu SO, Enwerem NM, Orisedipe A, Kubmarawa D, Gamaniel KS. Evaluation of the aqueous extract of *Boswellia dalzielii* stem bark for antimicrobial activities and gastro intestinal effects. African Journal of Biotechnology. 2004;3(5):284-288.
- Hassan HS, Musa AM, Usman MA, Abdulaziz M. Preliminary phytochemical and anti-spasmodic studies of the stem bark of *Boswellia dalzielii*. Nigerian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences. 2009;8(1): 1-6.
- Onoriose DA, Uwakwe AA, Monago CC. Hepatoprotective effect of the methanolic leaf extract of *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch on carbon tetrachloride induced hepatotoxicity in wistar rats. Indian Journal of Medicine and Healthcare. 2012;1(3): 55-63.
- Onobrudu DA, Ikewuchi JC, Onyeike EN. Moderation of ocular markers of oxidative stress of selenite-induced cataractous

- pups by *Boswellia dalzielii* Hutch Extract. Global Advanced Research Journal of Medicinal Plant. 2016;4(2):007-011.
11. Younoussa L, Elias NN, Danga YSP, Okechukwu E. Larvicidal activity of *Annonasene galensis* and *Boswellia dalzielii* leaf extract against *Aedesaegypti* (Diptera: colicidac). International Journal of Mosquito Research. 2014;1(4):25-29.
 12. Mariita RM, Ogol CKPO, Oguge NO, Okemo PO. Methanol extract of three medicinal plants from Samburu in Northern Kenya show significant anti-mycobacterial, anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties. Research Journal of Medicinal Plants. 2011;5:54-64.
 13. Wall ME, Eddy CR, McClennan ML, Klump ME. Detection and estimation of steroidal sapogenins in plant tissue. Analytical Chemistry. 1952;24:1337-1341.
 14. Wall JM, Krider MM, Krewson CR, Eddy CR, Willaman JJ, Corel DS, Gentry HS. Steroidal sapogenins. Survey of plants for steroidal sapogenins and other constituents. Journal of American Pharmacy Association. 1954;63:1-7.
 15. Trease GE, Evans WC. Pharmacognosy. 15th Ed. London: Saunders Publishers. 2002;42-393.
 16. Kone-Millogo H, Lompo M, Kini F, Asimi S, Guissou IP, Nacoulma O. Evaluation of flavonoids and total phenolic contents of stem bark and leaves of *Parkiabiglobosa* (Jacq) Benth, (Mimosaceae)-free radical scavenging and anti-microbial activities. Research Journal of Medical Sciences. 2009;3(2):70-74.
 17. Khan AK, Rashid R, Fatima M, Mahmood S, Mir S, Khan S, Jabeen N, Murtaza G. Pharmaceutical activities of protocathechuic acid. Acta Poloniase Pharmaceutica Drug Research. 2015;72(4):643-650.
 18. Sahil K, Souravh B. A review on protocathechuic acid and Its pharmacological potential. ISRN Pharmacology. 2014;1-9.
 19. Roberta M, Carmela S, Massimo D, Fabio G. Protocatechuic acid and human disease prevention: Biological activities and molecular mechanisms. Current Medicinal Chemistry. 2012;19(18):2901-2917.
 20. Li X, Wang X, Chen D, Chen S. Antioxidant activity and mechanism of protocathechuic acid *in-vitro*. Functional Foods in Health and Disease. 2011;7:232-244.
 21. Abida KK, Rehana R, Nighat F, Sadaf M, Sadullah M, Sara K, Nyla J, Ghulam M. Pharmacological activities of protocathechuic acid. Acta Poloniase Pharmaceutica Drug Research. 2015; 72(4):643-650.
 22. Tuty A, Tai A, Tomoyuki Y, Itani T. Antioxidative activity of catechin contents of four kinds of Uncariagambir extracts from West Sumatra Indonesia. African Journal Biochemistry Research. 2011; 5(1):33-38.
 23. Jeong WS, Kong ANT. Biological properties of monomeric and polymeric catechins: Green tea catechins and polycyanidins. Journal Pharmaceutical Biology. 2004;42:84-93.
 24. Colon M, Nerin CC. Role of catechins in the antioxidant capacity of an active film containing green, green coffee and grape fruit extracts. Journal Agricultural and Food Chemistry. 2012;66(39):9842-9849. DOI: 10.1155/2007/45673
 25. Gidaro MC, Astorino C, Petzer A, Carradori S, Alcaro F, Costa G, Artese A, Rafele G, Russo FM, Petzer JP, Alcaro S. Kaempferol as selective human MAO-A inhibitor: Analytical detection in calabrian red wines, biological and molecular modelling studies. Journal of Agriculture and Food Chemistry. 2016;64:1394-1400.
 26. Mira L, Fernandez MT, Santos M, Rocha R, Florencio MH, Jennings KR. Interactions of flavonoids with iron and copper ions: A mechanism for their antioxidant activity. Free Radical Research. 2011;36:1199-208.
 27. Smith AJ, Oertle J, Warren D, Prato D. Quercetin: A promising flavonoid with a dynamic ability to treat various diseases, infections, and cancers. Journal of Cancer Therapy. 2016;7:83-95.
 28. Balazs L, Leon M. Evidence of an oxidative challenge in the alzheimer's brain. Neurochemical Research. 1994; 19:1131-1137.
 29. Ansari MA, Hafiz MA, Joshi G, Opii WO, Butterfield DA. Protective effect of quercetin in primary neurons against a β

- (1-42): Relevance to alzheimer's disease. The Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry. 2009;20:269-275.
Available:<http://dx.doi.org/10.116/j.jnutbio.2008.03.002>
30. Maraini G, Mangili R. The human lens in relation to cataract: Differences in proteins and in the water balance of the lens in nuclear and cortical types of senile cataract; 2008.
DOI: 10.1002/9780470720028.ch5
31. Bigoniya P, Rena AC. Radioprotective and in-vitro cytotoxic sapogenin from *Euphobia nerifolia* leaf. Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Reseach. 2009;8(6):521-530.

© 2017 Onobrudu; This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:
The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
<http://sciencedomain.org/review-history/20146>